

Synthesis of highly functionalised 3-oxatricyclo[6.2.0.0^{2,6}]decanes towards the synthesis of kelsoene and spatol[†]

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The tricyclic compounds **9** and **20** have been synthesised towards the total synthesis of the sesquiterpene kelsoene and the diterpene spatol respectively. The key step involved intramolecular [2+2] photocycloaddition of 1,6-dienes embodied in a carbohydrate unit. The carbohydrate unit has been found to have profound influence on the stereochemical outcome during cycloaddition.

The linearly arrayed tricyclic skeleton containing four and five membered rings constitutes two different families of naturally occurring molecules – the sesquiterpenes kelsoane e.g. kelsoene **1**¹ and the diterpenes spatane e.g. spatol **2**². These two families are related to each other in the sense that the core structural units tricyclo 4-5-5 and 5-4-5 systems present in kelsoane and spatane respectively are biosynthetically derived from a common aromadendrane type precursor³. Several members of both these families possess antifungal and cytotoxic activity. The unique structure, multiple functionalities, stereochemical complications and the biological activities associated with these molecules have attracted global attention of the synthetic chemists^{4,5}. In view of our continued interest⁶ in the application of [2+2] photocycloaddition reaction in organic synthesis, we became interested to develop a general approach for entry into both these families. The preliminary results of this investigation is reported here.

Results and discussion

A retrosynthetic analysis (Scheme 1) of the structures **1** and **2** reveals the tricyclic system **3** having a sugar ring as an advanced intermediate. The sugar ring in the tricycle **3** provides opportunity for the synthesis to be an asymmetric

one. In addition, an appropriate sugar unit in **3** can be modified to provide the tricarbocyclic 4-5-5 system present in kelsoane. The 5-4-5 tricyclic system of the spatanes can be accessed by ring closure of the substituents R³ followed by opening of the sugar unit. The key intermediate **3** having a *cis-anti-cis* configuration, in principle, be obtained by an intramolecular [2+2] photocycloaddition of the 1,6-diene **4**.

Scheme 1

1,2 : 5,6-Di-*O*-isopropylidene- α -D-ribo-hexofuran-3-*ulose* **5**⁷, easily available from D-glucose, was chosen for the synthesis as it will provide the oxa-analogue of 4-5-5 ring system present in kelsoane. Reaction of the ketone **5** with methylmagnesium chloride afforded the carbinol **6** (Scheme 2). The hydroxyl group in it was then protected to afford the methyl ether **7** (NaH-THF-HMPA-MeI) in 89% yield. Selective removal of the acetonide moiety at the 5,6-position of the diacetone **7** with 75% aqueous acetic acid followed by treatment of the resulting diol with I₂-PPh₃ afforded the diene **8** in 55% yield. Irradiation of an ether solution of this diene in the presence of CuOTf as catalyst afforded the tricyclic adduct **9** in 77% yield. The gross structure of the product **9** was evident from its ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra. The stereochemical assignment is based on comparison of the coupling constant between the C₂-H and C₁-H with those reported for the proton α to the hydroxy group in *exo*-2-hydroxy bicyclo[3.2.0]heptane **10** (*J* 4.5 Hz)

[†]Dedicated to Professor S. M. Mukherji, an eminent Organic Chemist and the First Head of the Department of Organic Chemistry at IACS.

and endo-2-hydroxy bicyclo[3.2.0]heptane **11** (J 6 Hz)⁹. The C₂-H in the photoadduct **9** appeared at δ 4.43 as a doublet with a coupling constant of 6.0 Hz which diatates a *syn* relationship between the C₂-H and C₁-H. Thus, photocycloaddition of the diene provided an easy access to the 4-5-5 tricyclic system present in kelsoene, although it failed to establish the desired *cis-anti-cis* configuration present in kelsoene.

Scheme 2. Reagents and conditions: (i) CH₂=C(Me)CH₂MgCl, THF, r.t., 70%; (ii) NaH, THF, CH₃I, reflux, 2 h, 89%; (iii) (a) 75% aq AcOH, r.t., 12 h, (b) I₂, PPh₃, imidazole, PhMe, reflux, 2 h, 55%; (iv) h ν , CuOTf, Et₂O, 3.5 h, 77%.

The unexpected formation of the thermodynamically less stable *cis-syn-cis* adduct **9** may be attributed as follows. It is well established¹⁰ that copper(I) catalysed intramolecular [2+2] photocycloaddition requires formation of Cu^I complexes with diene as bidentate ligand prior to cycloaddition. The *endo* Cu^I complex **12** which could give rise to *cis-anti-cis* adduct is sterically crowded over the Cu^I complex **13**. Thus, photocycloaddition takes place through the complex **13** to afford the *cis-syn-cis* adduct **9**.

We next focussed on the synthesis of the tricyclic adduct **20** appropriately functionalised for the construction of the 5-4-5 system present in spatol **2**. Towards this end the unsaturated ester **17** was prepared from the ketone **5** following the literature procedure^{6m} as delineated in Scheme 3. Addition of allyl magnesium bromide to the ketone **5** followed by protection of the hydroxyl group in the resulting carbinol **14** gave the benzyl ether **15**. Oxidative cleavage of the alkene to the aldehyde **16** followed by Wadsworth-Emmons modified Wittig reaction afforded the unsaturated ester **17** in overall excellent yield. Selective deprotection of the 5,6-acetonide moiety followed by cleavage of the

Scheme 3. Reagents and conditions: (i) CH₂=CHCH₂MgBr, THF, r.t., 80%; (ii) NaH, BnBr, THF, reflux, 2 h, 70%; (iii) OsO₄, NaIO₄, H₂O, Et₂O, 79%; (iv) NaH, (EtO)₂P(O)CH₂CO₂ Et, THF, r.t., 18 h, 67%; (v) (a) 75% aq AcOH, r.t., 12 h, (b) NaIO₄, H₂O, CH₂CN, CCl₄, r.t., 52%; (vi) NaH, (EtO)₂P(O)CH₂CO₂Et, THF, r.t., 18 h, 65%; (vii) h ν , PhCOPh, CH₃CN, 54%.

resulting diol with sodium metaperiodate afforded the aldehyde **18** in 52% yield. Wittig reaction of this aldehyde using the modified procedure of Wadsworth-Emmons afforded the diene **19** in 65% yield. Irradiation of an acetonitrile solution of the diene **19** in presence of benzophenone as sensitizer afforded the tricyclic adduct **20** in 54% yield. The stereochemical assignment to the photoadduct **20** was made by detailed analysis of its ¹H NMR spectrum. The characteristic feature of the spectrum that led to *cis-syn-cis* assignment of the 4-5-5 ring system is the appearance of C₂-H as a doublet at δ 4.55 with J 5.4 Hz, comparable with the J value (6 Hz) observed for C₂-H in the analogous structure **9**. The stereochemical assignment at C₉ and C₁₀ relies on the coupling constants between the pairs C₁-H, C₁₀-H and C₈-H, C₉-H. The C₁₀-H appeared at δ 3.05 as a doublet of doublet with coupling constants of 4.8 Hz and 9.6 Hz, while the C₉-H appeared at δ 3.65 (dd) with coupling constants of 3.9 Hz and 9.8 Hz. The larger coupling constants (9.6 Hz) are indicative of the *anti* relationship between C₁₀ and C₁ hydrogens on comparison with J values observed for vicinally substituted cyclobutane derivatives^{6j}. The smaller coupling constant values (4 Hz) are due to coupling be-

Scheme 4

tween the two *syn* hydrogens at C₉ and C₁₀. The tricyclic adduct **20** is appropriately functionalised with correct stereochemical feature required for synthesis of spatol.

Sensitised photocycloaddition of 1,6-diene ester has

earlier been reported¹¹ to lead to a mixture of cyclobutanes with the ester units occupying both *exo* and *endo* positions. Exclusive formation of the adduct **20** in which the COOEt units are *exo*-oriented over the structure **21** may be explained in view of the well established mechanism¹², involved in a sensitised [2+2] photocycloaddition process (Scheme 4). Triplet sensitisation of one of the conjugated ester moieties in the diester **19** leads to the biradical intermediate **22**. 5-*exo*-Trig addition of the high-energy β -radical to the β -carbon of the other α,β -unsaturated ester unit may give rise to a new biradical with two different stereo disposition of the ester units as depicted by the structures **23** and **24**. Ring closure then takes place in the 1,4 biradical intermediate **24** which is less crowded compared to the cage-shaped structure **23** and gives rise to the adduct **20**.

In conclusion, we have developed an approach based on intramolecular [2+2] photocycloaddition of dienes built on a sugar template to construct highly functionalised tricyclic molecules related to natural products. Further, this investigation has demonstrated that a sugar template profoundly influences the stereochemical outcome in [2+2] photocycloaddition.

Experimental

All reactions were carried out under a blanket of N₂. Melting points were taken in open capillaries in a sulfuric acid bath and are uncorrected. Petroleum ether refers to the fraction having b.p. 60–80°. A usual work-up of the reaction mixture consists of extraction with ether, washing with brine, drying over Na₂SO₄, and removal of solvent in vacuo. Column chromatography was carried out with silica gel (60–120 mesh). Peak positions in ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra are indicated in ppm downfield from internal TMS in δ units. Unless otherwise stated NMR spectra were taken in CDCl₃ solution at 300 MHz for ¹H and 75 MHz for ¹³C. ¹³C Peaks assignment is based on DEPT experiment. IR spectra were recorded as neat.

1,2 : 5,6-Di-O-isopropylidene-3C-(2'-methyl-2'-propenyl)-3-O-methyl- α -D-allofuranose 7 :

A solution of the tertiary alcohol **6** (550 mg, 1.7 mmol), prepared according to the literature procedure⁸ in THF (5 ml) was added dropwise to a magnetically stirred suspension of NaH (130 mg, 2.6 mmol, 50% in oil), (freed from adhering oil by repeated washing with petroleum ether) in THF (5 ml). The mixture was gently refluxed for 2 h and cooled to r.t. To it was added HMPA (0.5 ml) followed by CH₃I (0.2 ml, 3.5 mmol). After refluxing for 2 h, the reaction mixture was cooled to r.t. and quenched by adding satu-

rated NH₄Cl solution (2 ml). Usual work-up of the reaction mixture followed by column chromatography using ether-petroleum ether (1 : 9) as eluent afforded the methyl ether **7** (510 mg, 89%) as a colourless viscous liquid; ¹H NMR δ 1.29 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.32 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.39 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.55 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.83 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.99 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz), 2.65 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz), 3.49 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.85 (1H, m), 4.00–4.12 (3H, m), 4.50 (1H, d, *J* 3.4 Hz), 4.87 (2H, d, *J* 18.5 Hz), 5.51 (1H, d, *J* 3.4 Hz); ¹³C NMR δ 24.5 (CH₃), 25.8 (CH₃), 26.8 (CH₃), 27.6 (CH₃), 36.1 (CH₂), 53.6 (CH₃), 69.1 (CH₂), 72.8 (CH), 82.7 (CH), 83.7 (CH), 102.9 (CH), 104.9 (C), 110.0 (C), 113.1 (C), 115.4 (CH), 141.5 (CH₂).

1,2 -Di-O-isopropylidene-3C-(2'-methyl-2'-propenyl)-3-O-methyl-4 β -ethenyl- α -D-allofuranose 8 :

A solution of the diacetone **7** (1.16 g, 3.5 mmol) in aqueous acetic acid (1.1 ml, 75%) was stirred at r.t. for 12 h. The reaction mixture was diluted with ethyl acetate (50 ml) and washed repeatedly with saturated aqueous NaHCO₃ solution (5 \times 5 ml). The organic layer was dried and concentrated to afford a colourless viscous liquid (900 mg). To a solution of this liquid in toluene (40 ml), was added imidazole (850 mg, 12.5 mmol) and PPh₃ (3.2 g, 12.5 mmol). This mixture was refluxed gently and iodine (2.36 g, 9.4 mmol) was added in small portions. Refluxing was continued for 2 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to r.t. and aqueous NaOH solution (10 ml, 20%) was added to it. Usual work up of the reaction mixture followed by column chromatography using ether-petroleum ether (1 : 19) as eluent afforded the diene **9** (490 mg, 55%) as a colourless viscous liquid; ¹H NMR (60 MHz) δ (CCl₄) 1.30 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.50 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.80 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.05 (1H, s), 2.1 (1H, s), 3.2 (3H, s, OMe), 4.3 (1H, d, *J* 3.6 Hz), 4.55 (1H, d, *J* 6 Hz), 4.70–4.90 (2H, m), 5.0–5.35 (2H, m), 5.45 (1H, d, *J* 3.6 Hz), 5.50–6.0 (1H, m).

cis-syn-cis-4 α ,5 α -di-O-isopropylidene-6 α -methoxy-8 α -methyl-3-oxatricyclo[3.2.0.0^{2,6}]decane 9 :

A solution of the diene **8** (900 mg, 3.51 mmol) in dry ether (180 ml) was irradiated with a 450 W Hanovia medium pressure mercury vapour lamp for 4 h in the presence of CuOTf (30 mg). The reaction mixture was washed with 30% aqueous ammonia solution (2 \times 30 ml) and dried. Removal of ether followed by column chromatography of the residual mass using ether-petroleum ether (1 : 19) as eluent afforded the photoadduct **9** (700 mg, 77%) as a white crystalline solid, m.p. 56–57°, [α]_D²⁵ + 47.17 (*c* 5.2, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR δ 1.23 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.36 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.58 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.75–2.04 (6H, m), 2.35–2.46 (1H, m), 3.31 (3H, s, OMe), 4.43 (1H, d, *J* 6 Hz), 4.46 (1H, d, *J* 3.6 Hz), 5.9 (1H, d, *J*

3.6 Hz); ^{13}C NMR δ 13.0 (CH₂), 26.7 (CH₃), 27.0 (CH₃), 27.7 (CH₃), 34.1 (CH₂), 43.3 (CH₂), 46.8 (CH), 52.3 (OCH₃), 80.2 (CH), 87.2 (CH), 90.6 (C), 97.4 (C), 106.1 (CH), 112.5 (C) (Found : C, 65.95; H, 8.51. Calcd for C₁₄H₂₂O₄ : C, 66.12; H, 8.72%).

1,2-Di-O-isopropylidene-3C-(4'-carboethoxy-2'-butenyl)-3-O-benzyl 4 β -formyl- α -D-allofuranose 18 :

A solution of the diacetone **17** (300 mg, 0.64 mmol) in aqueous acetic acid (3 ml, 75%) was stirred at r.t. for 12 h. The reaction mixture was diluted with ethyl acetate (30 ml) and washed repeatedly with saturated aqueous NaHCO₃ solution (2 \times 5 ml). The organic layer was dried and concentrated to afford a colourless viscous liquid (250 mg). A solution of this diol (250 mg, 0.59 mmol) in CH₃CN (4 ml) was added to a magnetically stirred suspension of NaIO₄ (190 mg, 0.88 mmol) in water (5 ml) at r.t. Stirring was continued for 1 h. The mixture was filtered. Usual work-up of the filtrate followed by column chromatography using ether-petroleum ether (1 : 3) as eluent afforded the aldehyde **18** (130 mg, 52%) as a colourless viscous liquid; IR : 1720.4, 1652.9 cm⁻¹; ^1H NMR δ 1.26 (3H, t, *J* 7.1 Hz, CH₃), 1.36 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.59 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.60 (2H, m), 4.16 (2H, q, *J* 7.1 Hz, COOCH₂CH₃), 4.51 (1H, d, *J* 3.5 Hz), 4.69 (2H, s, OCH₂Ph), 4.74 (1H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz), 5.83 (1H, d, *J* 3.6 Hz), 5.88 (1H, d, *J* 15.8 Hz), 6.90 (1H, dt, *J* 7.6 Hz), 7.26–7.42 (5H, m, ArH), 9.69 (1H, s, CHO); ^{13}C NMR δ 14.2 (CH₃), 26.6 (CH₃), 26.9 (CH₃), 33.9 (CH₂), 60.6 (CH₂), 67.7 (CH₂), 82.4 (CH), 84.7 (CH), 85.8 (C), 104.0 (CH), 113.6 (C), 126.1 (CH), 127.6 (CH), 127.7 (CH), 128.4 (CH), 137.5 (C), 140.5 (CH), 165.6 (CO), 198.1 (CHO).

Synthesis of the diester 19 :

To a magnetically stirred suspension of NaH (120 mg, 2.48 mmol, 50% in oil) freed from adhering oil by repeated washing with petroleum, was added a solution of triethyl phosphonoacetate (0.6 ml, 2.88 mmol) in dry THF (5 ml) dropwise at room temperature. The resulting clear solution was stirred at r.t. for 40 min and to it the aldehyde **18** (800 mg, 2.06 mmol) in dry THF (5 ml) was added dropwise. Stirring was continued for additional 12 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to 0° and quenched by adding saturated aqueous NH₄Cl (5 ml). Usual work-up of the reaction mixture followed by column chromatography [ether-petroleum ether (1 : 4)] afforded the α,β -unsaturated ester **19** (620 mg, 65%) as a colourless viscous liquid : IR : 1721.3, 1715.3, 1657.9, 1651.0 cm⁻¹; ^1H NMR δ 1.22–1.30 (6H, m), 1.37 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.60 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.44 (1H, ddd, *J* 1.5, 7.0, 13.6 Hz), 2.57

(1H, ddd, *J* 1.1, 7.9, 15.1 Hz), 4.14–4.22 (4H, m, COOCH₂CH₃), 4.51 (1H, d, *J* 3.7 Hz), 4.64 (1H, d, *J* 10.6 Hz, PhCH), 4.73 (1H, d, *J* 10.6 Hz, PhCH), 4.83 (1H, dd, *J* 2.0, 3.9 Hz), 5.74 (1H, d, *J* 3.6 Hz), 5.85 (1H, d, *J* 15.5 Hz), 6.15 (1H, dd, *J* 2.1, 15.9 Hz), 6.89–7.01 (2H, m), 7.26–7.40 (5H, m, ArH); ^{13}C NMR δ 14.57 (CH₃), 14.60 (CH₃), 26.9 (CH₃), 27.2 (CH₃), 34.7 (CH₂), 60.8 (CH₂), 60.9 (CH₂), 67.92 (CH₂), 80.2 (CH), 82.2 (CH), 85.4 (C), 104.2 (CH), 113.6 (C), 123.3 (CH), 125.4 (CH), 127.5 (CH), 128.0 (CH), 128.1 (CH), 128.5 (CH), 128.7 (CH), 138.2 (C), 141.7 (CH), 142.4 (CH), 166.1 (CO), 166.2 (CO).

cis-syn-cis-4 $\alpha,5\alpha$ -Di-O-isopropylidene-6 α -hydroxy-9,10-dicarboethoxy-3-oxatricyclo[3.2.0.0^{2,6}]decane 20 :

A solution of the unsaturated ester **19** (240 mg, 0.52 mmol) in acetonitrile (130 ml) was irradiated in the presence of benzophenone (80 mg, 0.44 mmol) through a water-cooled pyrex immersion well with a medium-pressure mercury vapour Hanovia Lamp (450 W) for 3 h. The solvent was removed under vacuum. The residue was chromatographed [ether-petroleum ether (1 : 5)] to afford the cyclobutane derivative **20** (130 mg, 54%) as a colourless viscous liquid : $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{20} + 36.8^\circ$ (*c* 0.8, CHCl₃); IR : 1737.7, 1732 cm⁻¹; ^1H NMR δ 1.01–1.26 (6H, m, COOCH₂CH₃), 1.40 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.61 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.50 (1H, dd, *J* 8.4, 14.9 Hz), 3.05 (1H, dd, *J* 4.8, 9.6 Hz), 3.19–3.29 (2H, m), 3.65 (1H, dd, *J* 3.9, 9.9 Hz), 4.49 (1H, d, *J* 11.1 Hz), 4.55 (1H, d, *J* 5.4 Hz), 4.62 (1H, d, *J* 3.9 Hz), 4.63 (1H, d, *J* 11.1 Hz), 5.97 (1H, d, *J* 3.6 Hz), 7.26–7.47 (5H, m, ArH); ^{13}C NMR δ 14.2 (CH₃), 26.8 (CH₃), 27.0 (CH₃), 37.4 (CH), 37.6 (CH₂), 39.7 (CH), 41.8 (CH), 46.7 (CH), 60.6 (CH₂), 60.7 (CH₂), 67.2 (CH₂), 80.5 (CH), 84.9 (CH), 98.2 (C), 106.3 (CH₂), 113.0 (C), 127.6 (CH), 127.7 (CH), 128.4 (CH), 129.7 (C), 172.8 (CO), 173.1 (CO) (Found : C, 65.63; H, 6.88. Calcd. for C₂₅H₂₇O₈ : C, 65.20; H, 7.00%).

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